

DEVELOPING PRONUNCIATION SUBSKILLS OF PUPILS

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Annotation: The article is dedicated to the problem of developing pronunciation subskills of the pupils of linguistic educational institutions based on principle of maximum approximation.

Key words: the principle of maximum approximation, pronunciation subskills, linguistic educational institutions.

Language can perform its function as the most important means of human intercourse only as a language of sounds, because spoken words in all languages consist of speech-sounds, and speech without words is impossible. Letters only serve to represent spoken words in written form. But, words pronounced or written in isolation cannot express complete thoughts. More or less complete thoughts can only be expressed in sentences consisting of one or several words put together according to the grammar rules of the language and pronounced with the proper intonation.

As a means of communication by word of mouth, language is used in oral speech and in reading aloud. Therefore, in order to make oneself easily understood while expressing one's own or other people's thoughts in any language by means of oral speech or reading aloud, one must be able to pronounce sentences in that language quite correctly. Teachers and pupils of a foreign language must also be able to pronounce isolated words and even separate sounds correctly, both in their mother tongue and in the foreign language.

One must also have a good pronunciation in order to be able to understand other people easily when they speak or read aloud. This is proved by the well-known fact that the better we pronounce a foreign language the easier we understand it when we hear it. The teacher of a foreign language must also be able to teach the correct pronunciation of that language.

Therefore, one of the principle aims of would-be teachers of a foreign language is to master both the pronunciation of the language they are going to teach and the methods of teaching pronunciation.

The general teaching objectives for the first semester of a university course of practical phonetics and phonology for English philology should include the following activities:

- auditory discrimination between apparently similar English phonemes;
- accurate production of English speech sounds in isolation words and longer utterances first by imitation, then in prompted production tasks (reading) and finally in free production in communication;
- elimination of common pronunciation mistakes and strong foreign accent.

In order to meet the requirements it is advisable for the pupils to develop different levels of language awareness in the area of pronunciation, such as:

- Phonological awareness – understanding the sound structure of spoken word;

The awareness and capability of aurally perceiving speech sounds of a language and consciously manipulating the speech organs to produce particular sounds in speech;

- Phonemic awareness – the awareness of the existence of phonemes as smallest individual sound units that make up words and whose manipulation can change the meaning of utterances as in minimal pairs;

- Phonics awareness – the discovery of sound-spelling correspondence rules.

First year at university is the most complete, informative, responsible and at the same time interesting and productive. On the first year of their study pupils get all the necessary knowledge about such particular aspect of language as phonetics.

In order to achieve this aim they must have a clear idea of what a good pronunciation is, what the difficulties in acquiring it are, and how these difficulties can be overcome. To have a good pronunciation means:

1. To articulate correctly all the speech sounds of the language and all their combinations in their proper order not only in isolated words, but also in sentences;

2. To pronounce sentences fluently at the speed required by the situation, with correct stresses, melody, tempo, rhythm and pauses.

In order to acquire orthoepic pronunciation in a foreign language the learner must first of all know exactly what to do with his organs of speech to produce the necessary speech sounds [3, 78].

Many of the speech sounds in any language have one or more articulatory, and therefore, acoustic, features in common which serve as a basis for grouping these sounds together in definite classes.

When the student has learnt acoustic features in common and by what terms these common features are and remembered what groups of speech sounds have the same articulatory and acoustic features in common and by what terms these common features are designated, that is to say, when he has learned the classification of speech sounds, it will be easier for him to remember the articulation of each sound. He will not have to memorize the full description of the articulation. It will be sufficient for him to remember only characteristic of each sound given in terms which stand for these articulatory and acoustic features. Then he will be able to give a full description himself without learning it beforehand.

The phonetic laws of a language reflect its phonetic structure, or system, its basis is formed by its system of phonemes.

The phoneme is the smallest unit of language existing as such a speech sound which is capable of distinguishing one word from another, otherwise alike, or on grammatical form of one word from another form of the same word. For example, the English words [bi:d] and [bid] and [bæd] and [bed] are distinguished one from another by the vowel sounds. The vowel sounds in man and men differentiate two grammatical forms of the noun man: the singular and the plural forms. Therefore, these different sounds represent different phonemes of the English language as it was explained in previous subchapter. The different consonant sounds [s] and [z] distinguish from each other such words as advice and advise, therefore, they also represent different English phonemes.

It is clear from the examples that the correct pronunciation of sounds representing different phonemes is indispensable for the recognition, and therefore for the understanding of words. That is enough for pupils of non-linguistic institutions, but in order to get maximum approximate pronunciation pupils must be aware of variants of phonemes, allophones.

Teacher must pay attention to training pronunciation. Pupils listening to authentic speech, not only learn the right way of pronunciation of English phonemes, but also prepare themselves for the perception of fast and continuous English speech.

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